

DEMAND MAPS

PROBLEM ENCOUNTERED AND OBJECTIVE

The uptake of reusable food packaging across Europe is uneven, influenced by local awareness levels, regulatory complexity, and perceived practicality. While interest in reuse is increasing, operators often lack reliable, location-specific demand signals to guide deployment. The objective was to design and implement social media awareness campaigns in three European regions, combine myth-busting with calls to action, and translate qualitative and quantitative engagement data into Demand Maps supporting reuse packaging decision-making.

MAIN RESULTS / OUTCOMES

The campaigns revealed clear regional differences in reuse maturity and stakeholder readiness. Tampere showed strong engagement and an emerging market requiring concrete reuse options, while Madrid demonstrated growing awareness constrained by regulatory complexity and economic concerns, particularly in hospitality. Switzerland displayed stable but non-mainstream adoption, indicating systemic barriers. Engagement rates ranged from excellent (Tampere, Madrid) to moderate (Switzerland), generating robust datasets transformed into comparative regional Demand Maps.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Demand Maps should be used as dynamic planning tools to align reuse solutions with local readiness levels. Regions with high engagement, such as Tampere, should prioritise rapid deployment of ready-to-use systems, while cities like Madrid require regulatory clarification and economic incentives alongside awareness efforts. In mature but stagnant contexts such as Switzerland, systemic measures beyond communication are needed. Social media campaigns should be geographically targeted and repeated to monitor demand evolution over time.

Further information

All the demand maps can be found here: [STOPP PROJECT DEMAND MAPS](#)

About this abstract

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STOPP is a Horizon Europe project aiming to transform food plastic packaging through the “5 Rs”: Refuse, Reduce, Redesign, Reuse, and Recycle. Aligned with the EU’s Packaging Directive, it develops training materials and strategies to promote circular economy solutions. Engaging stakeholders, STOPP advances recycling, reusable packaging, and consumer awareness for sustainable food packaging.

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